

Online Core Flux Reconstruction Using Ex-core Neutron Detectors and Assembly Thermocouples

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ABSTRACT

The neutron flux monitoring is important for ensuring the reactor safety. However, the harsh core environment in liquid metal reactors makes the deployment of in-core neutron detectors rarely considered. More practical flux monitoring typically relies on ex-core neutron detectors and assembly thermocouples. This study proposes an online core flux reconstruction method that utilizes measurements from ex-core neutron detectors and assembly thermocouples to core flux monitoring. The proper orthogonal decomposition is utilized to generate a low-dimensional reduced basis space for state representation. To integrate ex-core neutron detector and assembly thermocouple measurements, a sparse measurement matrix is constructed, enabling the estimation of reduced basis projection coefficients. Numerical results for the MOX3600 benchmark case show that a reduced basis space with a dimension of 4 achieves sufficient approximation performance. Using 24 thermocouples with a noise level of 0.01, the maximum node-wise reconstruction error is 25%, which is further reduced to 15% when ex-core neutron detector measurements is incorporated.

Keywords: Online Core Flux Reconstruction, Liquid metal reactors, Ex-core Neutron Detector, Assembly Thermocouple

1. INTRODUCTION

Liquid metal reactors (LMRs) are fast-spectrum nuclear reactors that use liquid metals as coolants. Two types of LMRs, the sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs) and the lead-cooled fast reactor (LFRs), are considered among the six Generation IV nuclear energy systems. These reactors play a crucial role in reducing radioactive waste and optimizing uranium resource utilization. During the operation of a nuclear reactor, the neutron flux monitoring system is indispensable. It provides critical information, including power level, reactivity, neutron flux distribution, and other essential parameters. Due to the high neutron flux and high-temperature environment within the core of LMRs, the deployment of in-core neutron detectors is rarely considered. This makes it challenging for liquid metal reactors to achieve core flux reconstruction or mapping based on in-core neutron detector measurements, as is achievable in pressurized water reactors (PWRs) [1]. In LMRs, more practical methods for measuring flux or power include the use of ex-core neutron detectors and the estimation of assembly thermal power based on temperature measurements from assembly thermocouples [2, 3]. Developing an online core flux reconstruction method based on these available measurements is important for monitoring and ensuring the operational safety of LMRs.

In this paper, we try to develop an online core flux reconstruction method based on ex-core neutron detectors and assembly thermocouples within the framework of model order reduction and sparse sampling. Similar reconstruction framework using ex-core neutron detectors has been proposed and discussed in previous studies [4, 5]. In our work, we use Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [6]

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to obtain low-dimensional reduced bases, enabling the core state to be represented using only a small number of projection coefficients. Furthermore, we define a sparse measurement matrix specifically tailored to the measurements from ex-core neutron detectors and assembly thermocouples. The combination of model order reduction and sparse sampling enables the projection coefficients to be estimated from limited measurements, thereby achieving core flux reconstruction.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical and methodological foundations of this study, including the reduced basis space generation, the measurement matrix construction, and the online flux reconstruction method. Section 3 shows the numerical results and analysis for a SFR case, focusing on the approximation performance of the generated reduced basis space and the evaluation of core flux reconstruction error under different measurement configurations and noise levels. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the conclusions of this study.

2. THEORY AND METHODS

2.1. Reduced basis space generation

The POD is a widely used dimensionality reduction technique for constructing low-dimensional reduced basis spaces. Consider a collection of samples $\{\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^N\}_{k=1}^M$, where each sample, also referred to as a snapshot, represents a state vector defined over a spatial domain of interest $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and depends on the parameter μ_k . These snapshots are characterized by a high dimensionality N , which is typically determined by the spatial mesh discretization. The snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ is constructed as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1 \quad \mathbf{x}_2 \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{x}_M] \quad (1)$$

Mathematically, the POD is closely related to the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). The SVD of the snapshot matrix provides a unique matrix decomposition expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^* = \sum_{k=1}^M \sigma_k \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^* \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is an orthogonal matrix containing the left singular vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_k\}_{k=1}^N$, $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$ is a diagonal matrix containing the singular values $\{\sigma_k\}_{k=1}^N$ arranged in descending order, $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$ is an orthogonal matrix containing the right singular vectors $\{\mathbf{v}_k\}_{k=1}^M$, and the superscript $*$ denotes the matrix transpose. The singular values quantify the contribution of their corresponding singular vectors, enabling the identification of a low-dimensional subspace that captures the dominant modes of the snapshots. Specifically, we can retain the leading r ($r < M \ll N$) singular values $\{\sigma_k\}_{k=1}^r$ and their corresponding singular vectors, while discarding the remaining singular values and singular vectors. This process is referred to as truncated SVD, which is expressed as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{\Sigma}_r \mathbf{V}_r^* = \sum_{k=1}^r \sigma_k \mathbf{u}_k \mathbf{v}_k^* \quad (3)$$

The truncated SVD generates the reduced basis space \mathbb{V}_{rb} , which is spanned by $\{\mathbf{u}_k\}_{k=1}^r$, also referred to as the POD modes. A given sample \mathbf{x} can be projected onto the \mathbb{V}_{rb} , thereby transforming its representation from the original N -dimensional space to the r -dimensional \mathbb{V}_{rb} , effectively reducing the dimensionality. The projection $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ and the projection error are calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{x} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{U}_r \alpha = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{U}_r^* \mathbf{x} \quad (4)$$

$$\|\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}\|_2 = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{U}_r^* \mathbf{x}\|_2 \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is the projection coefficient vector, and $\|\cdot\|_2$ is L_2 -norm. To control the projection error, a suitable truncated rank r is typically selected using the formula $\sum_{k=1}^r \sigma_k^2 / \sum_{k=1}^M \sigma_k^2 \geq \eta$, where $\eta \in (0, 1)$ is a user-defined truncated threshold that determines the proportion of the cumulative energy retained in the reduced basis space.

2.2. Measurement matrix construction

The measurement matrix $\mathbf{S}^* \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times M}$ represents a set of measurements on the snapshot \mathbf{x} , as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_1} & \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_2} & \cdots & \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_p} \end{bmatrix}^* \mathbf{x} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the measurement vector consisting of measurement values $\{y_k\}_{k=1}^p$ at the measurement locations $\{\gamma_k\}_{k=1}^p$, $\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is a column vector, and $y_k = \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^* \mathbf{x}$. If the measurement value y_k depends only on the state at the measurement location γ_k , i.e., pointwise measurements, \mathbf{s}_{γ_k} is the γ_k -th canonical unit vector. The measurement matrix composed of canonical unit vectors is typically employed in neutron flux monitoring using in-core neutron detectors [7]. When the snapshot \mathbf{x} is a flux vector Φ , multiplying the canonical unit vector yields the flux measurement value at the location of the in-core neutron detector $y = \mathbf{s}^* \Phi$. This paper focuses on the construction of the measurement matrix based on the ex-core neutron detectors and assembly outlet thermocouples.

For ex-core neutron detectors, the classical ex-core neutron detector response model defines the ex-core neutron detector measurement as a weighted sum of the core power or fission source distribution [8], as follows:

$$y = \int d\mathbf{r} w(\mathbf{r}) S(\mathbf{r}) \quad (7)$$

where $S(\mathbf{r})$ represents the core power or fission source distribution, and $w(\mathbf{r})$ is a spatial weighting function for the ex-core neutron detector, also known as detector response function (DRF). Considering the fission source distribution and spatial discretization, the column vector \mathbf{s} of the ex-core neutron detector is expressed as follows:

$$y = \mathbf{s}^* \Phi = \sum_{k=1}^N w_k v \Sigma_{f_k} \phi_k \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{s}^* = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 v \Sigma_{f_1} & w_2 v \Sigma_{f_2} & \cdots & w_N v \Sigma_{f_N} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $v \Sigma_f$ is the fission neutron production cross-section.

For assembly outlet thermocouples, the assembly thermal power P is estimated from the coolant temperature measurements [3], as follows:

$$P = Q C_P (\bar{T}) \Delta T \quad (10)$$

where Q is the coolant flow crossing the assembly, C_P is the coolant specific heat capacity evaluated at the mean coolant temperature \bar{T} , $\Delta T = T^{\text{outlet}} - T^{\text{inlet}}$ is the measured temperature difference between the inlet and outlet coolant of the assembly, and \bar{T} is typically estimated as $0.5 \times (T^{\text{inlet}} + T^{\text{outlet}})$. In this study, the inlet coolant temperature is kept constant, so the temperature difference ΔT is determined solely by the outlet coolant temperature measurements of assembly outlet thermocouples. If the fission power of the assembly i is approximated by its thermal power, the following equation can be derived:

$$y_i = \Delta T_i = \frac{P_i}{Q_i C_P (\bar{T}_i)} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N I_{\mathbf{r}^i}(\mathbf{r}^k) \kappa \Sigma_{f_k} \phi_k}{Q_i C_P (\bar{T}_i)} \quad (11)$$

where $\kappa \Sigma_f$ is the fission energy production cross-section, $I_{\mathbf{r}^i}(\mathbf{r}^k)$ is the indicator function, \mathbf{r}^i represents the spatial domain of the assembly i , and \mathbf{r}^k represents the spatial domain of mesh k . The indicator

function is defined as, when $\mathbf{r}^k \subset \mathbf{r}^i$, $I_{r^i}(\mathbf{r}^k) = 1$, otherwise, $I_{r^i}(\mathbf{r}^k) = 0$. Then, the column vector \mathbf{s} in $y = \mathbf{s}^* \Phi$ is given by the following expression:

$$\mathbf{s}^* = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{I_{r^1}(\mathbf{r}^1) \kappa \Sigma_{f_1}}{Q_i C_P(\bar{T}_i)} & \frac{I_{r^1}(\mathbf{r}^2) \kappa \Sigma_{f_2}}{Q_i C_P(\bar{T}_i)} & \dots & \frac{I_{r^1}(\mathbf{r}^N) \kappa \Sigma_{f_N}}{Q_i C_P(\bar{T}_i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

2.3. Online flux reconstruction

If the snapshot is represented in the reduced basis space \mathbb{V}_{rb} , the measurement vector is expressed as $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r \alpha$. When the number of measurements is greater than or equal to the dimensionality of the reduced basis space ($\mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times r}$, $p \geq r$), the projection coefficient vector α can be estimated solely from the measurements \mathbf{y} using interpolation ($p = r$) or least-squares regression ($p > r$) without requiring knowledge of the complete state vector \mathbf{x} . Consequently, the state vector can be reconstructed as follows:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \begin{cases} (\mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^{-1} \mathbf{y}, & p = r \\ (\mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^\dagger \mathbf{y}, & p > r \end{cases} \Rightarrow \hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{U}_r \hat{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

The above process minimizes the sum of squared residuals $\text{RSS} = \sum_{k=1}^p (y_k - \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^* \hat{\mathbf{x}})^2$. In measurements obtained from the ex-core neutron detectors and assembly outlet thermocouples, the measurement values $\{y_k\}_{k=1}^p$ from the two instruments may differ significantly in scale. Consequently, due to the differences in scale, the contributions of the measurement values with smaller scales become almost negligible during the minimization of RSS. To balance the contributions of the two kinds of measurements to the RSS, the vector $\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^*$ and the measurement y_k are scaled according to the norm $\|\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^*\|_2$, as follows:

$$\text{RSS} = \sum_{k=1}^p \left(\frac{y_k - \mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^* \hat{\mathbf{x}}}{\|\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_k}^*\|_2} \right)^2 = \sum_{k=1}^p (\bar{y}_k - \bar{\mathbf{s}}_{\gamma_k}^* \hat{\mathbf{x}})^2 \quad (14)$$

This is equivalent to solving a weighted interpolation or least-squares regression problem with the weight matrix $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag} \left[\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_1}^*\|_2}, \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_2}^*\|_2}, \dots, \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{s}_{\gamma_p}^*\|_2} \right]$, as follows:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \begin{cases} (\mathbf{W} \mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^{-1} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{y} = (\bar{\mathbf{S}}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{y}}, & p = r \\ (\mathbf{W} \mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^\dagger \mathbf{W} \mathbf{y} = (\bar{\mathbf{S}}^* \mathbf{U}_r)^\dagger \bar{\mathbf{y}}, & p > r \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The reconstruction performance is relative with the measurement matrix \mathbf{S}^* , which is constructed based on the measurement locations. Therefore, optimizing the placement of ex-core neutron detectors and assembly outlet thermocouples is important. The placement of ex-core neutron detectors is limited and also needs to consider the requirements for axial offset and radial quadrant tilt monitoring. In contrast, the placement of assembly outlet thermocouples offers greater flexibility for optimization. In our work, the placement of outlet thermocouples is optimized based on the Q-DEIM and GappyPOD+E algorithms [9, 10]. It aims to construct the measurement matrix by greedily optimizing specific matrix functions of $\mathbf{S}^* \mathbf{U}_r$, such as the determinant and eigenvalues. For more specific details, please refer to [7, 11].

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Problem description and sample collection

MOX3600 is a 3600 MWth SFR featuring a large-size oxide fuel core [12]. The core is composed of 453 fuel assemblies and 33 control assemblies. It is divided into two zones: the inner core, which

consists of 225 fuel assemblies, and the outer core, which consists of 228 fuel assemblies. The control rod assemblies are divided into two control systems. The primary control system consists of six control assemblies located in the inner core and 18 control assemblies positioned at the interface between the inner and outer core zones. The secondary control system includes nine control assemblies situated in the 7th row. The parameters considered in the sample collection include the burnup process and the insertion depth of control assemblies in the primary control system. A 400-day burnup process with a time interval of 100 days is considered, resulting in five burnup state points. The control assemblies move within the active core region with a step length of 6.7044 cm. The insertion of control assemblies is radially symmetric, resulting in 16 insertion depth state points. The dataset comprises $M_1 = 5 \times 16 = 80$ training samples. Additionally, a separate set $M_2 = 60$ of test samples was generated exclusively for evaluation purposes. Figure 1 illustrates the sampling distribution within the parameter space.

The coupled neutronic/thermal-hydraulic simulation of the MOX3600 reactor is based on the multi-physics simulation framework MORPHY developed in the previous study [13, 14]. In each simulation, the neutron scalar flux at each fuel region node is collected and arranged into a state vector. The 12 ex-core neutron detectors are divided into two groups and placed at two different levels of the core. For each ex-core neutron detector, the DRF is generated by performing multiple multi-group fixed-source simulations using OpenMC [15]. Figure 1 shows the core configuration and the detector response functions.

Figure 1. The core configuration, detector response functions and parameter sampling distribution.

3.2. Generation of reduced basis space

The snapshot matrix, constructed from the training samples, is utilized to generate the reduced basis space through the SVD. Figure 2 shows the singular values, cumulative energies, and projection errors as functions of the increasing the truncated rank r . It can be observed that the singular value and projection error decay rapidly. The cumulative energy analysis indicates that the leading 4 singular values account for 99.99% of the total energy. The truncation rank $r = 6$ is chosen, yielding projection errors of 2.40×10^{-3} and 1.89×10^{-3} for the training sample and test samples, respectively. The reduced basis space is spanned by the leading 6 left singular vectors. Figure 2 illustrates the leading 4 POD modes. It can be observed that POD modes 1 and 2 primarily capture the overall distribution features of the flux. This explains their association with larger singular values, as they form the cornerstone of the state reconstruction. POD modes 3 and 4 focus more on capturing the distinctive features among the samples, such as localized flux changes caused by different control assembly positions.

Figure 2. Reduced basis space generation and POD modes.

3.3. Online flux reconstruction

Figure 3 shows the optimized placement for different numbers of assembly outlet thermocouples. Figure 4 shows the flux reconstruction errors under various assembly outlet thermocouple placements and whether the measurements from ex-core neutron detectors are considered. Gaussian noise in the mea-

Figure 3. The optimized placements of assembly outlet thermocouples.

surements y_i with a standard deviation of σy_i is considered. The reconstruction error is calculated as $\epsilon = \frac{1}{50 \times M} \sum_{i=1}^{50} \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{\|\hat{x}_k - x_k\|_2}{\|x_k\|_2}$. It can be observed that the reconstruction error increases as the noise level rises. Increasing the number of assembly outlet thermocouples helps reduce the reconstruction error under noisy conditions. However, the improvement effect reaches a threshold: the improvement from increasing the number of thermocouples from 6 to 12 is more significant than the improvement from increasing the number from 12 to 24. When ex-core neutron detectors are used, the effect of reducing reconstruction error by increasing the number of assembly outlet thermocouples becomes less significant. This is likely because the ex-core neutron detectors have already provided supplementary measurement information. Overall, the reconstruction error with ex-core neutron detectors is lower than that without them. Figure 4 also shows the node-wise flux reconstruction error using 24 assembly outlet thermocouples. Similarly, the improvement effect of using ex-core sensor measurements on flux reconstruction can be observed. The reconstruction performance is similar between the training sam-

ples and test samples. When ex-core sensors are used, the maximum node-wise reconstruction error is approximately 25%, compared to 15% when they are not used.

Figure 4. The flux reconstruction errors with or without (*w* or *w/o*) the ex-core neutron detectors.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In LMRs, due to the harsh core environment, in-core neutron detectors are rarely considered. Therefore, achieving online core flux reconstruction based on available measurements is important for monitoring and ensuring operational safety. This paper develops an online core flux reconstruction method based on measurements from ex-core neutron detectors and assembly outlet thermocouples. The POD is used to generate a low-dimensional reduced basis space, allowing core states to be represented by a small number of projection coefficients. By integrating it with the constructed sparse measurement matrix, the projection coefficients can be estimated from limited measurements, thereby enabling efficient core flux reconstruction. Numerical results for the MOX3600 case show that, when considering the variations in control rod movement and burnup within the sample, a reduced basis space of dimension 6 achieves sufficient approximation performance. The reconstruction error depends on the number of measurements and the measurement noise level. With 24 thermocouples and a measurement noise level of 0.01, the maximum node-wise reconstruction error is 25%. By further incorporating measurements from ex-core neutron detectors, the maximum node-wise reconstruction error is reduced to 15%. These preliminary results demonstrates the feasibility of the developed online core flux reconstruction method. Future work will focus on further refinements and error analyses.

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